

THE ELIZABETHAN WORLD, ITS BACKGROUND AND ITS LEGACY

Discourse

Of the Gloriana Society

Spring
2017

IN THIS ISSUE

All the News – Members Only

by Angela Ranson

Reminder

(About the Newsletter)

This newsletter aims to bring together work by scholars and enthusiasts. While there is no requirement for contributions to be written by people who have studied the Elizabethan world in an academic context, we do intend to include only legitimate, well-researched content. Thus, this newsletter will be an opportunity for our members to share the topics that interest them, as well as advertise upcoming events and projects.

Society Update

The Society has launched several new initiatives since beginning its second year in existence in January 2017. Our new members-only forum is growing in popularity, and we have held our first Q&A session, 'A Private Audience with Susan Doran.' We also held a great postgraduate workshop at York on 13 March.

About the 2018 Conference

We are pleased to announce the title of our 2018 conference: '**The Tudor Dynasty: State, Realm and the Early Modern World**'. Further information will be announced in May.

Meet Our Members

Nicole Lamont, second-place winner of the Best Paper Award at the 2016 'In the Light of Gloriana' Conference, describes her current research interests

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'In the Light of Gloriana' Conference Reflections

Lucinda Pope, Rena Bood and Sabine Waasdorp reflect back on the inaugural conference.

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Plus:

There is a special announcement about an exciting upcoming Gloriana Society event on page 12.

Also, find announcements about upcoming books on page 10, and calls for submissions on page 5 and 9.

Christian Humanism and the Notion of 'The Turk'

By Gunay Heydarli

Through the centuries the Turkish threat has been studied as a source of fear and unrest. From the mid-fifteenth century onwards, the dominant image of the Turk focused on the Ottomans as a power. That image was developed particularly in response to the landmark events of the Ottoman advance, the fall of Constantinople in 1453, the siege of Rhodes and capture of Otranto in 1480, the destruction of the Mamluk sultanate in 1516-1517 and the defeat of the Hungarians at Mohacs in 1526. Although Christians were terrified that Turks would conquer Europe and impose Islam, they also envied and admired Ottoman religious unity, administration and military. Western authors started to focus on the culture, religion and organization of the Ottoman Empire as an imminent threat to Europe[6,90].

The fact that the Turks made it so far into Europe, even to the point of threatening Germany, the heartland of the Reformation, shocked and terrified Christians. Given the terrible divide in Christendom, Erasmus of Rotterdam and Martin Luther, the giants of Christian Humanism and the Protestant Reformation respectively, surprisingly agreed on the merits of a defensive war.

In Luther's view of the world the mutual antagonism of pope and sultan was irrelevant: they were both agents of the devil. As he put it in *On the War Against the Turks* (1529): 'Just as the pope is the Antichrist, so the Turk is

very devil incarnate'. Luther refers to some who were favorable to the Ottoman Empire ;who actually want the Turk to come and rule, because they think that our German people are wild and uncivilized - indeed that they are half-devil and half-man'. He further remarks that 'although some praise the Turk's government because he allows every one to believe what he will so long as he remains temporal lord, yet this reputation is not true, for he does not allow Christians to come together in public', certainly halfhearted condemnation at most [10, 156].

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This appraisal came in 1529, even as Suleyman besieged Vienna, whose fall seemed imminent. Sultan Suleiman expanded the borders of the Ottoman Empire to its farthest, enriched its wealth to the highest and delivered the biggest progress in law, art, and architecture. Europeans both feared and admired the power of the Ottomans Turks during his reign and rightfully called him the "Grand Turk"[5,148].

Luther's anti-Turk position had been initially shared by Erasmus. In his letter to Paul Volz Erasmus criticizes the crusade ideal by exposing the harshness of prevailing attitudes towards the Turks. Drawing on early Christian thought-not medieval accretions or

crusade apologias- he asks what will become of the Turks if Leo X's proposed crusade succeeds. Christians should endeavor to convert the Turks, just as Christ bade his followers do with all unbelievers [3,116]. He echoed Nicholas Cusa's optimistic view that the Turks were already 'half-christian'. Most early Christians, however, saw the Turks and Islam in very different terms. In 1530, Erasmus wrote a short treatise entitled *De bello Turcico*, in which he suggested that Christians were a greater threat to their tarnished faith than an external enemy like the Turks[4,140].

Erasmus also loved the ideals of peace and order. As such, he recognized war as an extension of the right of the government to dispense justice and establish order. Erasmus wrote, 'But if Christians are to be entirely denied the right to make war, by the same reasoning magistrates will have to lose the right to punish offenders. For war is no more than judicial retribution meted out on a large scale'.

Western writers were obsessed with the looming Turkish menace, so they often wrote about Ottoman military strength. Many writers concluded that the Ottoman Turks' tremendous ability of warfare and military discipline were the main reasons behind their success and found these characteristics admirable. For example, Sebastian Munster, a German scholar and cosmographer, was one of the first authors to write about the military characteristics of the Ottoman Turks in his book, *Cosmographia*, published in 1544. According to Munster, although Turks were 'cruel' people, they were also to

be admired in many respects, such as their ‘soldiership’. Munster wrote: ‘Nothing is more marvelous about the Turk than their speed in action, constancy in danger and obedience towards their empire’. He praised the Turkish army and described them as ‘honest, without indecency, given neither to sedition nor to rioting, they hope not for revelry, but merely to kill or be killed for the Empire’ [2,119].

The military organization and martial discipline of the Turks were also underscored in the *Short Treatise upon the Turkes Chronicles* (1546), which was translated by Peter Ashton into English from Paulo Giovio’s *Comentario de le cose de Turchi* (1532). In the book, the last section, titled ‘The Array and Discipline of the Turkish Warfare’, points out the military methods of the Turks and provides advice on how to use the Christian armies against them. At the time, Christian Europe did not have a standing army, but rather depended on emergency or volunteer recruits, who were mostly ill-trained and resentful, with poor discipline and no unity. In contrast, the Ottoman Turks’ regular professional army, recruited from their subject populations, was regarded with awe and admiration due to its discipline and organization. Giovio underscores this lack of unity and discipline against the Turkish army and concludes that there might be hope to defeat the Turks only if the Christian princes are unified. He states: ‘if the Christian princes were so wholly of one mind and consent, that at the first rumour of the Turks coming they would assemble and

gather together power and strength of men able to resist and withstand him. But certes we can scant trust that this shall happen’ [11, 157].

A thinker such as Jean Bodin could write in open admiration about Ottoman society: ‘The king of Turks who rules over a great part of Europe, safeguards the rites of religion as well as any prince in this world. Yet he contrains no one, but on the contrary permits everyone to live as his conscience dictates. What it more, even his seraglio at Pera he permits the practice of four diverse religions, that of the Jews, the Christian according to the Roman rite, and according to the Greek rite, and that of Islam’ [7,178]. Bodin held the empire up as a model of religious toleration. Compared with other states as the Habsburgs, the French, the Venetian or the Russian this argument certainly holds, and it probably also is valid in comparison with those modern nation states that define citizenship exclusively in fabricated categories of ethnicity, race or religion.

In conclusion, we can say that the Ottomans became the great warriors of Islam, creating a world empire that incorporated major Muslim centers like Cairo, Baghdad, Damascus, Mecca and Medina. They threatened the heart of Europe for almost two centuries. From the fifteenth to the seventeenth century Ottoman forces seemed invincible to European Christians [1,148]. Both internal and external threats to the existence Christendom created the need to define the “Turk” in such terms that the image of Turk may either be justifiable or demeaning, depending on the political,

religious, or ideological allegiance. The historical texts, treatises, and essays reviewed so far show that Europeans had mixed feelings towards the Ottoman Turks during the 16th and 17th centuries. They admired and envied the success of the Ottoman administration, organization and the military discipline as well as the bravery and fortitude of the Turkish soldier. On the other hand, Turks were characterized as cruel, merciless, which is a continuation of the stereotypical Turkish image that was dominant in the preceding Western discourse.

ANNOUNCEMENT GLORIANA SOCIETY EVENT

A trip to
Kenilworth
Castle
10 June, 2017

Members: £5.00
Non-Members: £8.50
(Spaces are limited. It will be first come, first served)

For more information or to book your spot, visit our website at
www.glorianasociety.org